

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Özer, Ö. K., & Topal, Y. E. (2022). The Role of Gender in Turkish Solar Energy Research. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2237). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6906465>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

The Role of Gender in Turkish Solar Energy Research

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Introduction

The effects of gender on scientific productivity, the impact of publications, national and international cooperation, and research grants are hot topics in the literature (Klev et al., 2020; Lawson et al., 2021; Thelwall, 2018; Kwiek & Roszka, 2021). Although it varies depending on discipline, country, and age, the scientific productivity of female researchers is lower than that of male researchers (Bentley, 2012; van Arensbergen et al., 2012). Productivity is critical for promotion and access to research funds, and even low female representation gets lower as the academic level rises (Ferrari et al., 2018; Ghiasi et al., 2021).

Although the rate of female researchers at Turkish universities is higher than in many countries, the number of male researchers in engineering and basic sciences is relatively higher (O’Neil et al., 2019). By this motivation, we aim to examine whether this imbalance in gender equality is the case for interdisciplinary solar energy (SE) research.

Using bibliometric data, we examined SE research in Turkey to reveal whether the gender of the researcher influences publication productivity and impact. Our research question is: "What role does gender play in SE research in Turkey?" The present study aims to make a descriptive contribution to gender (in)equality discussions in Turkey (Bülbül, 2021; Ucal et al., 2015).

Methods and Materials

We used the data of 2990 scientific publications indexed by the Web of Science (WoS) between 2001 and 2020. Our analysis will be further improved by the data of 655 doctoral dissertations on SE derived from the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) Database of Turkey.

The role of gender in SE research is revealed by analysing the rate and productivity of authors in scientific publications and the changes over time. This study is a preliminary work to describe the current situation and the reasons.

We made a bibliometric analysis of Turkey (TR)-addressed (all) publications on SE. The dataset was downloaded in June 2021 using the SE-related part of the query developed by Armitage et al. (2020).¹ After eliminating the irrelevant publications, we identified 2990 publications that include at least one TR-addressed (co)author.

To detect the gender of the authors, first, we partitioned the author full names into first names and surname(s), uniformed the author names and assigned a unique ID to each author. Afterwards, the authors' genders were identified by matching their first names with the database of "genderize.io", an online tool that provides the probability of gender for names (Lund and Shamsi, 2021). We note that it is somewhat easy to distinguish first names from surnames in Turkey. Women generally are registered by their spouse's surname after marriage, and keeping the maiden name is optional. In Turkish academia, women researchers generally continue to use their maiden names. Turkish names are mostly not unisex, and this is an advantage for our study.

The names of Turkey-based authors are matched with the "genderize.io" considering the probability of gender and the usage count. Then, we checked the CoHE Academic Information System and relevant websites for the unisex names. We classified authors whose names are Turkish and have two surnames as female. Also, we cross-checked the genderize.io database by using US Social Security Administration name data between 1950 and 2020.

We identified 5736 unique authors of 3544 affiliated with at least one TR-addressed organisation while 2192 authors are from other countries. We could detect more than 96% of TR-addressed authors' gender (Table 1).

Table 1. Gender distributions of researchers in TR-addressed publications

Author Gender	TR-addressed	Other countries	Total
Female	998 (28.2%)	305 (13.9%)	1303 (22.7%)
Male	2430 (68.6%)	1362 (62.1%)	3792 (66.1%)
Not Found	116 (3.27%)	525 (24.0%)	641 (11.2%)
Total	3544	2192	5736

Findings and Discussion

Our analysis shows that only 28.2% of authors who affiliated with at least one TR-addressed organisation between 2001 and 2020 is female (Table 1). The number of female authors who published first time in SE is about half of the new male authors entered the field since 2010 (Figure 1).

TR-addressed publications began to increase, particularly after 2010 and exceeded 400 in 2020 (Figure 2). The numbers of publications authored by only males and that of mixed (male & female) have increased. However, the share of publications authored by only female authors has decreased despite the increase in female doctoral graduates.

¹ The query could be shared upon request.

Figure 1. The number of new authors by gender and year

Source: Authors' calculation from WoS data

Figure 2. TR-addressed publications by year

Source: Authors' calculation from WoS data

Figure 3. Distribution of the same-sex collaboration

The median same-sex co-authoring ratio for women is 0.333 and for men is 0.889 (the ratio is zero if the author has no co-authored publication with same-sex researchers and equals one if all publications of an author are co-authored with same-sex researchers). The median ratio for all researchers is 0.75. As indicated by these ratios and Figure 3, male researchers tend to co-author with men. The female authors also tend to work with men. Also, men produce more single-authored publications than women produce (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Single-authored publications by gender

The median number of publications (co)authored per year is 0.333 for male and female authors affiliated with at least one TR-based organisation. The mean numbers of publications per year produced by female (0.526) and male (0.531) authors indicate that the average productivity of female and male authors is similar. However, the top female author could produce about 3.5 publications per year, while several male authors could publish more than four papers (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Publication per year by gender over time

The publications in which women contributed have been cited less than those including male (co)authors. The share of single-authored publications with no citations is similar for women and men (Figure 6). The median CNCI value of publications female authors contributed is lower than that of men (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Share of documents with no citation by gender composition and co-authorship type

Figure 7. Category normalised citation impact (CNCI)

Conclusion

Our preliminary findings show that average productivity is almost the same for both genders. However, the most prolific authors are generally men. Female authors are apt to work in teams rather than publishing alone. Our findings confirm Kwiek and Roszka (2021) regarding gender homophily in scientific publications while opposing the literature finding that men tend to cooperate with men and women with women. The likelihood of being cited is lower for the publications female authors contributed.

In the following steps, we will examine the role of gender in collaboration and the mobility of researchers within and outside the country. The role of gender on research fields and the change of network parameters by gender will be analysed to examine the impact of the research field on gender and productivity relationship.

Acknowledgement

This work was catalyzed by the SolarTwins project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 856619. The SolarTwins project covered all conference costs.

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